

THE INTERACTION OF COMPETITION AND MONOPOLY

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In the context of the desire of each market entity to maximize profits and, consequently, to expand the scale of economic activity, firms act as competitors in relation to each other. Economic competition refers to the competition of economic agents in the consumer market.

The emergence of monopolies is a historically inevitable economic process caused by the development of centralization, concentration of production and scientific and technological progress. Despite the negative phenomena, monopolies have firmly entered the economy of most countries.

Until about the middle of the 19th century, the economies of developed countries were characterized by perfect competition, which was determined by the small size of enterprises and the large number of manufacturers. But since the second half of the century, the picture has begun to change significantly: large enterprises are gradually capturing an increasing share of markets. The rapid development of production, associated with the rapid growth of capital-intensive heavy industries, railway construction, and the transition to the use of electric energy, led to the formation of large and super-large enterprises. The following data indicate the increased concentration of production at the turn of the XIX -XX centuries. In Germany, large enterprises (with more than 50 workers) accounted for 0.3% of all enterprises in 1882, and 22% of all workers in the country were concentrated on them; in 1925, large enterprises accounted for 1.2% of the total number of enterprises and 48% of the total number of workers. In 1904, American industry had the largest enterprises with a production volume of \$1 million. They accounted for 9.9% of the total number, and employed 25.6% of workers.

In 1909, such enterprises already accounted for 1.1% of the total number, and they employed 30.5% of all workers who produced 43.8% of the country's total industrial output. These processes have led to a significant change in the nature of competition in the markets.

The most in-depth and complete analysis of radically new moments in the behavior of economic agents in markets and new market conditions was given in the fundamental works "The Economic Theory of Imperfect Competition" by Joan Robinson and "The Theory of Monopolistic Competition" by Edward Chamberlin.

The conditions under which economic competition takes place are usually referred to as a market structure. It is characterized by a number of features: the number and size of firms, the type of product offered, the degree of price control, the conditions for entering and exiting the industry, and the reliability of information.

Despite the variety of market structures, the following four market models are usually distinguished: perfect and imperfect competition, including monopolistic competition, oligopoly and monopoly. Each of these structures differs in the degree of market competitiveness, that is, the ability of firms to influence the market structure. The less

influence this has from the company's branches, the more competitive the market is considered to be.

The presented characteristics of the types of market structures, when compared with reality, show that such market models as perfect competition and monopoly are actually extremely rare, while monopolistic competition and oligopoly are actually present in all existing markets of the world. With perfect competition, there are a large number of sellers competing in the market. The volume of production and supply from individual manufacturers account for a small proportion of total output, so one firm cannot have a noticeable impact on market prices.

Participants in a competitive market have equal access to information, that is, all sellers have an idea of the price and possible profit. In turn, buyers are aware of the prices. There is freedom to enter and enter the market.

In practice, perfect competition in its pure form is a rare phenomenon. But there are a number of industry markets that have exactly this structure. For example, markets for agricultural products, markets for a number of services. These markets include a large number of independent sellers offering standardized goods, the price of which is determined by the ratio of supply and demand.

Imperfect competition is understood as a market in which at least one of the conditions of perfect competition is not fulfilled. In most real markets, the vast majority of products are offered by a limited number of firms. Large corporations, which have concentrated a significant part of the market supply in their hands, find themselves in a special relationship with the market environment. Firstly, by occupying a dominant position in the market, they can significantly influence the conditions of sale of products. Secondly, the relationship between market participants is also changing.

Imperfect competition is divided into three main types: monopolistic competition, oligopoly, and monopoly.

An example is the markets for clothing, shoes, washing powders, soaps, and soft drinks. Firms producing goods for this purpose, as a rule, operate in conditions of monopolistic competition. Goods of the same purpose are close substitutes, one may differ from the other in the quality of performance, packaging, design, and after-sales service. Thus, firms compete by selling differentiated products. Product differentiation allows the manufacturer to set the price independently, regardless of the actions of competitors. Each company is the only manufacturer and, in this sense, a monopolist. But since the sales volume of each seller is relatively small, each of the firms has limited control over the market price.

Entry into the market of monopolistic competition is quite free and is determined mainly by the size of each participant's capital. However, entering the market is difficult compared to free competition.

An oligopoly is a market dominated by several large firms. It is difficult to determine the exact number of firms, since the oligopolistic market covers a fairly large part of the national market.

Firms make high profits because access to the oligopoly market is significantly difficult. Penetration into the industry is hindered by almost the same barriers as in the conditions of a monopoly. Among the most important are the amount of capital required for a new company to enter the industry, as well as the control of existing manufacturers over the latest

technology and production technology. The oligopolistic market is characterized by the interdependence of several rivals. Since only a few firms compete in the market, each market participant must carefully monitor the behavior of rivals, weigh their actions in relation to pricing policy, and assess the economic consequences of their decisions.

Depending on the type of product, a pure oligopoly and a differentiated one are distinguished. Enterprises of a pure oligopoly produce a homogeneous standardized product: aluminum, cement, chemical or steel industry products. The identity of these goods determines the single price for them. An oligopoly that produces a variety of products of the same functional purpose is called differentiated. Usually differentiated oligopolies specialize in the production of consumer goods, such as cars, tires, cameras, household appliances, cigarettes. An oligopoly as a market structure includes a cartel, which is a collusion of several firms over prices and output volumes in order to maximize joint profits. If all the enterprises of the industry unite into a cartel, then it behaves like a monopolist firm.

A monopoly is a large corporation that occupies a leading position in a certain area of the national economy, which determines the economic behavior of the firm. There may be a situation in the market when buyers are confronted by a monopolist entrepreneur who produces the bulk of a certain type of product. In this case, a small company may turn out to be a monopolist. Conversely, a large firm may not be a monopolist if its market share is small.

Monopoly assumes that there is only one manufacturer in the industry that fully controls the volume of product supply. This allows him to fully set the price that brings maximum profit. The extent to which monopoly power is used in setting prices will depend on the availability of close substitutes for the product. If the product is unique, the buyer is forced to pay the assigned price or refuse to purchase. The number of products that have no analogues is usually limited. A pure monopoly can include the provision of public utilities, cable television companies, telephone companies, or the monopoly of book publishing on the sale of textbooks, etc.

A monopolist firm usually has a higher profit, which naturally attracts other manufacturers to the industry. In the case of a pure monopoly, the barriers to entry into the industry are quite large, and this practically blocks the penetration of competitors into the monopolized market. The real barriers to entry into the industry are as follows.

First, there is the scale effect. Highly efficient production with low costs is achieved in conditions of large-scale production due to market monopolization. Such a monopoly is often called a "natural monopoly", that is, an industry in which average costs are minimal if only one firm serves the entire market. It is extremely difficult for new competitors to enter such an industry, since it requires large investments, and a monopolist firm, having lower production costs, is able to temporarily reduce the price of products and destroy a competitor.

Secondly, the presentation of exceptional laws. In a number of European, American and Russian countries, the government grants firms the status of sole seller for transport services, communications services, gas supply, etc. But in return for these privileges, the government reserves the right to regulate the actions of such monopolies in order to exclude abuse of monopoly power, protect the interests of non-monopolized industries and the population.

Thirdly, patents and licenses. The government guarantees patent protection for new products and manufacturing technologies, which provides manufacturers with a monopoly position in the market.

Fourth, ownership of the most important types of raw materials. Some companies are monopolists due to the undivided ownership of the sources of the production resource.

Sometimes, in order to generate additional income, a monopoly, using its market position, sells the same product at different prices in different markets. The practice of applying different prices on the part of the firm is called price discrimination. The use of such prices is not only possible due to the isolation of markets from each other by geographical or tariff barriers, but also becomes real due to the different response of demand to price changes (elasticity of demand) in these isolated markets, and, consequently, the willingness of individual consumers to purchase the necessary amount of goods at a price above the market.

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